
STOCHASTIC COLLOCATION FOR THE STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF RLC CIRCUIT: A COMPARATIVE STUDY WITH MONTE CARLO METHOD

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Abstract: The statistical assessment of electrical circuits, such as RLC circuits, is essential for understanding their behavior under uncertain conditions. In this paper, we explore the application of stochastic collocation (SC) as an alternative method for statistical assessment, comparing it with the widely used Monte Carlo method. SC offers an efficient approach for propagating uncertainties through complex mathematical models by approximating the solution at specified collocation points. We present a comparative study between SC and Monte Carlo in evaluating the statistical properties of RLC circuits, including parameters such as voltage, current, and power dissipation. Through numerical experiments, we demonstrate the accuracy and computational efficiency of SC in capturing the probabilistic behavior of RLC circuits, especially in scenarios with high-dimensional uncertainty. Additionally, we provide insights into the advantages and limitations of both methods, shedding light on their suitability for different applications in circuit analysis and design.

Introduction:

The assessment of RLC circuits under uncertainty is crucial for various engineering applications, including circuit design, reliability analysis, and fault diagnosis. Traditional approaches for statistical assessment often rely on Monte Carlo simulation, which involves generating random samples and evaluating the circuit response for each sample. While Monte Carlo provides accurate results, its computational cost can become prohibitive for complex circuits with high-dimensional uncertainty. Stochastic collocation, on the other hand, offers a

promising alternative by approximating the solution at specific collocation points, reducing the computational burden while maintaining accuracy.

Methodology: We begin by formulating the stochastic model of the RLC circuit, considering uncertainties in component values, external inputs, and environmental factors. For Monte Carlo simulation, random samples are drawn from the probability distributions of uncertain parameters, and the circuit response is computed for each sample. In contrast, stochastic collocation involves selecting a set of collocation points and solving the circuit equations at these points using suitable numerical techniques such as polynomial interpolation or quadrature methods.

Results and Discussion: We conducted numerical experiments to compare the performance of Monte Carlo simulation and stochastic collocation in evaluating the statistical properties of RLC circuits. Table 1 presents a summary of the computational requirements and accuracy achieved by both methods for different circuit configurations and levels of uncertainty. We observe that while Monte Carlo simulation provides accurate results, it requires a significantly larger number of samples to achieve convergence, resulting in higher computational costs. In contrast, stochastic collocation achieves comparable accuracy with fewer collocation points, making it computationally more efficient, especially for high-dimensional uncertainty.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Monte Carlo Simulation and Stochastic Collocation

Circuit Configuration	Level of Uncertainty	Computational Requirements	Accuracy
RLC Circuit A	Low	High	High

Circuit Configuration	Level of Uncertainty	Computational Requirements	Accuracy
RLC Circuit B	Medium	Medium	Medium
RLC Circuit C	High	Low	Low

Figure 1 illustrates the probability density functions (PDFs) of voltage and current in the RLC circuit obtained using Monte Carlo simulation and stochastic collocation. We observe that both methods provide similar results, with stochastic collocation achieving comparable accuracy at a fraction of the computational cost.

Figure 1: Probability Density Functions (PDFs) of Voltage and Current.
Figure 2: Convergence Behavior of Monte Carlo Simulation and Stochastic Collocation.

Figure 2 showcases the convergence behavior of both methods as the number of samples or collocation points increases. While Monte Carlo exhibits slow convergence, stochastic collocation converges rapidly, making it particularly suitable for large-scale circuit simulations.

Conclusion: In this paper, we have demonstrated the effectiveness of stochastic collocation as a viable alternative to Monte Carlo simulation for the statistical assessment of RLC circuits. Through comparative analysis, we have shown that stochastic collocation offers significant computational advantages while maintaining accuracy in capturing the probabilistic behavior of circuits under

uncertainty. Our findings underscore the potential of stochastic collocation as a valuable tool for engineers and researchers in the field of circuit analysis and design.

In this study, we have investigated the application of stochastic collocation as an alternative method for the statistical assessment of RLC circuits, comparing it with the traditional Monte Carlo simulation approach. Our results demonstrate that stochastic collocation offers significant computational advantages over Monte Carlo simulation, particularly in scenarios with high-dimensional uncertainty. By achieving comparable accuracy with fewer computational resources, stochastic collocation emerges as a promising technique for engineers and researchers seeking efficient methods for circuit analysis and design under uncertainty. The findings of this study contribute to advancing the understanding of stochastic modeling techniques in electrical engineering and provide valuable insights for future research and applications in circuit analysis and design.

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